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Control of TOX transcription factors by the Hippo signaling pathway.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
East Islip, NY USA 11730
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

We evaluated the hypothesis here that the exhaustion program, which we have found to be and described as intrinsically linked with senescence, receives inputs from the extracellular environment resulting from sensing of mechanical force, by measuring total transcription and monitoring TOX activation and repression following depletion of Hippo signaling components YAP and TAZ.

Results

We measured total transcription following genetic depletion of YAP and TAZ or enforced expression of YAP in human cells to evaluate the hypothesis that mechanical force, transduced through the Hippo pathway, informs or provides input to the exhaustion pathway whose gene expression program is regulated by the TOX family of transcription factors.

Figure 1: Silencing of YAP1 and TAZ results in TOX2 and TOX4 activation.

GSE54617

n=3 SK-Hep1 control siRNA
n=3 SK-Hep1 siRNA for YAP1 and TAZ

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_3230215	2.64e-14	-1.97e+01	22.962439	-2.04	TOX2	77/47231	99.8
ILMN_1743131	2.24e-04	-4.52	-0.095934	-4.46e-01	TOX4	4688/47231	90.1

Figure 2: Enforced expression of YAP1 results in silencing of TOX4.

n=2 MCF10A
n=2 MCF10A over-expressing YAP1

ID	p-value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
201683_x_at	0.082291	2.32	-3.882	6.94e-01	TOX4	5384/54670	90.2

Discussion

We found here control of TOX transcription factors, which are nuclear regulators of the exhaustion program, associated with the senescence program, by Hippo pathway signal transduction components YAP1 and TAZ.